

ESTIMATION OF BISMUTH. PART III. VOLUMETRIC ANALYSIS WITH PHENYLARSONIC ACID

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In a previous paper (Part I of this series, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1944, **21**, 119) it was shown that bismuth could be estimated gravimetrically by the reagent phenylarsonic acid and separated from elements such as silver, lead, mercury, copper, cadmium, tin, cobalt, nickel, zirconium, thorium, thallium, alkalis and alkaline earths by precipitating at a p_H of 5.2 to 5.3 in acetic acid solution, buffered with sodium or ammonium acetate.

The precipitate bismuth phenylarsonate can be used for the volumetric estimation of bismuth by dissolving it in hydrochloric acid, and reducing by hydriodic acid the pentavalent arsenic of phenylarsonate to trivalent state, which is again being oxidised by iodine solution. The method followed here is almost the same as that of Kolthoff (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1923, **62**, 137) recommended for the estimation of arsenic acid, with a little modification.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Bismuth was precipitated by the reagent following the procedures described in Part I of this series and using the same reagents. The precipitate thus obtained was well washed with hot water and transferred to a conical flask with water and concentrated hydrochloric acid in equal volumes. The volume of the solution should be kept as little as possible. This is then heated on a water-bath for about five minutes, and after the addition of 2.3 g. of potassium iodide again heated on the water-bath for 10-15 minutes and cooled under tap water. A few c.c. (1-2) of starch solution were added and the blue colour was just discharged by the dropwise addition of a decinormal solution of sodium thiosulphate. An excess of sodium bicarbonate was then added to the solution slowly with stirring, diluted to 200 c.c. and titrated with a standard solution of iodine. If during transference of the bismuth phenylarsonate a large quantity of water be added, that should be evaporated to dryness and then equal volumes of hydrochloric acid and water should be added. For calculation : $1 \text{ Bi} \equiv 1 \text{ As} \equiv 2 \text{ I}_2 \equiv 2 \text{ thiosulphate}$ or 1 c.c. of $N/10$ iodine solution = 0.01045 g. Bi.

Results

Bi taken.	Conc. HCl.	I ₂ soln. (0.0999N)	Bi found.	Bi taken.	Conc. HCl.	I ₂ soln. (0.0999 N/10)	Bi found.
0.02243 g.	2 c.c.	2.15 c.c.	0.02245 g.	0.1262 g.	6 c.c.	12.1 c.c.	0.1263 g.
0.0504	4	4.85	0.0506	0.1512	8	14.45	0.1509
0.0504	4	4.81	0.0502	0.0209	2	2.0	0.0209
0.0756	6	7.25	0.0757	0.0418	6	4.0	0.0418
0.1008	6	9.65	0.1007				

Concentrated hydrochloric acid, sodium bicarbonate, potassium iodide etc., used were all of 'pro analyse' variety of Kahlbaum.

Thus bismuth can be estimated volumetrically in presence of a number of elements, by the reagent phenylarsonic acid.

Micro-estimation of bismuth with this reagent is in progress.

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